

ORAL FOLK ART IN ELEMENTARY GRADES**Andijan State Pedagogical Institute,****associate professor****Ubaydullayev Ilkhomjon Sayfullaevich**

Annotation: In this article peculiarities of oral art, its types and importance were highlighted. Furthermore, methods of teaching oral folk art in elementary grades were discussed.

Key words: *community settings, folklorists, mainstream culture, Oral history, intergenerational nature, Cultural Awareness, Creative Expression, whimsical, critical thinking.*

The concept of folklore conjures up a variety of popular images. People are likely to think of fairy tales, trickster stories, quilting bees, herbal medicines, ballads, work songs, children's games and countless other cultural traditions. In fact, all of these are part of the folk process, and have been studied in community settings by folklorists around the world. They are considered folklore in that they are part of a body of traditional knowledge in the community, and they continue to be re-created, adapted and passed on through oral transmission. Historically, the discipline of Folklore has drawn from a wide range of approaches in studying traditional art forms. Early folklore research in the United States often involved the collecting of traditional materials, such as Cecil Sharp's well-known collections of English folksongs found in Southern Appalachia (1917).

This approach often seemed like a race with time, as folklorists sought to document and preserve songs and stories that would soon be lost to the oral tradition either because of technological advances, changing social conditions, or pressure to assimilate with mainstream culture[1]. As is persuasively stated by Cynthia Cohen (above), oral history is a vital educational tool, as well as a method for studying cultural and social history. The experiences of teachers around the

state re-affirm this position, and provide inspiring testimony about the value of integrating the folk arts and oral history with regular school curricula. Some of the educational benefits of these programs are outlined below: Oral history and the folk arts provide an easily accessible, engaging and participatory way for students to become involved in local history. In learning from other community members, students are also better able to understand their own place in the historical continuum. Because these studies are often of a cross-cultural and intergenerational nature, they lead to increased communication between students, family members and others in the community. They can also work towards the reduction of prejudice and discrimination by inspiring an appreciation for cultural diversity.

Folklore and oral history emphasize process as well as product, and therefore provide an effective way to focus on students' learning skills. Reading and writing, listening and speaking, and critical thinking skills are all enhanced by the interviewing and editing process. Approaching social and cultural issues through the arts may be more suitable to some individuals' learning styles; and students may learn on a more affective level through the arts than they would through other forms of instruction. Activities that involve music, dance and the visual arts also allow students to develop their own creativity, and to communicate feelings and ideas that might not be expressed through other media. The interdisciplinary nature of these approaches allows teachers to draw from rich musical, historical, literary, and cultural sources. Folk art can teach students about more than just art styles and techniques[2]! It can also help them understand the world and other cultures. Here are a few reasons to implement folk art projects:

- **Cultural Awareness:** Folk art can help elementary school students gain an understanding and appreciation for the art and culture of different countries and regions. When learning about folk art, you can talk about geography, history, and cultural transitions. What a great way to go cross-curricular!

- **Creative Expression:** Folk art can inspire students to express themselves creatively and develop their own unique styles. When studying folk art, students will get a chance to see various techniques, which can help them uncover their own unique style.
- **Hands-on Learning:** Many folk art projects involve hands-on techniques such as weaving, pottery, or paper cutting. Strengthen fine motor skills and introduce students to new artistic mediums through folk art.
- **Imagination:** A lot of folk art uses imaginative, whimsical, or symbolic elements. You can interpret these elements to develop students' critical thinking and encourage students to use their own imagination and think creatively when creating art.
- **Critical Thinking:** Speaking of critical thinking, with folk art projects, students will analyze the visual and cultural elements of a piece of art. They can also make connections between different works and cultural contexts. This will help deepen their critical thinking skills.

A feature of oral folk art(folklore) is its ancient origin, because such works were created at a time when there was no written language. Often a lot of people participated in the creation of a single work, each of them added something of their own when retelling. This is another feature - variability, because even one narrator or singer could not repeat the works many times without changes. Every person knows what is the oral folkcreation. His genres are almost all preserved to this day. Each of them reflects the thoughts and aspirations of the people, their attitude to the events taking place. A great place in the oral folklore is ritual folklore. Although this layer of folk culture is almost unknown now. There are some genres share folklore.

1. Fairy tales are the most common folkloreworks. Long since the children grew on Russian fairy tales. This has great educational significance. Folk tales are permeated with the spirit of patriotism, heroism and faith in the victory of good over evil.

2. A great place in oral folk art takes up the epic. It reflects the rich historical experience of the people in the struggle against conquerors and oppressors. Together, many narrators gradually formed a positive image of the hero - a defender and a hero who loves his homeland. The epic works also reflect the traditions of the people and their customs. Tradition is another feature that oral folklore has. Genres of the epic are epics, legends, historical songs and legends.
3. But the most common are now small genre oral folk art - jokes, proverbs, sayings, tongue twisters, poteshki and riddles. They are very diverse and constantly updated. Even in the modern era, despite the widespread use of written language, new sayings are being created, riddles and tongue twisters are being invented[3].

To conclude all given facts above it should be noted that examples of folk oral creativity, including Proverbs, fast speech, riddles, are important cultural treasures passed down by generations. Including these items in the language of the primary class and reading literacy classes can offer students a unique and interesting way to learn about different cultures and traditions. One of the reasons for the fact that in folk oral creativity the fairy-tale genre is well received and intrigued by children and read into images is the influence of the fairy-tale language, its upbringing, the appreciation of friendly relations, the constant triumph over evil, its sharpness, manners and closeness to the folk language. A fairy tale, proverb, narrative, narrative, narrative in folk oral creativity, most of the stories are real-life images, short characters from the events that took place merges with. A sharp, interesting plot of folk oral creativity, an extraordinary wonderful situation in the event rivija captivates children, the brave, strong, elegant, resourceful, courageous, brave agile heroes in them, the ideological direction of the fairy tale, in which goodness, strength - the everlasting fulfillment of good will make children feel overwhelmed. The form of acceptance, which is told in the fairy tale, is the same word and the

repetition of phrases over and over again, the tonality, the poignancy of their language, the vitality of the means of expression are very interesting for children. The participants in the fairy tale are often the personification of the merciful generous, the just, and the evil, the miserable, the greedy, the opposite of them[4]. The value of the teacher in the fairy tale is such that in children correctness in it wins honesty, poor people get rid of hardship, that is, good, goodness comes true they rejoice that they have come out and evil, evil has been condemned. They want it to be like this all the time in life and believe it. When a child believes in fairy tales, is interested, his worldview, thinking, knowledge will increase even more.

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